

PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF MEDICAL RECORDS OF INPATIENTS WITH GASTRITIS

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Abstract

The research was conducted based on the data of patients treated in the gastroenterology department of the Multidisciplinary Clinic of Tashkent State Medical University. The study included a retrospective analysis of the medical records of inpatients diagnosed with gastritis, as well as the examination and processing of statistical indicators, presenting pharmacoeconomic frequency-based results related to the use of medications.

According to the findings, in the treatment of gastritis, proton pump inhibitors -omeprazole, rabeprazole, and pantoprazole - were used with the highest frequency, accounting for a significant share of medication-related expenditures. The obtained results provide a basis for optimizing the timely supply of medicines to patients, improving the quality of inpatient treatment, and minimizing overall healthcare costs.

Keywords: gastritis, disease, medications, medical records, retrospective analysis, pharmacoeconomic frequency analysis.

Introduction. A number of retrospective and pharmacoeconomic frequency-based studies related to gastritis and its treatment have been conducted worldwide. In particular, these studies present the following findings.

Gastritis is an inflammation of the gastric mucosa and represents a disease characterized by substantial heterogeneity in its clinical presentation, etiology, and histopathological features. Recent analyses indicate that in 2021 the global number of patients with gastritis and duodenitis reached approximately 27.2 million, with an age-standardized incidence rate (ASIR – Age-standardized incidence rates) of 323.2 per 100,000 population. [4]. According to another source, in 2019 the global number of patients with gastritis and duodenitis reached 31 million, which represents an increase of 12 million compared to 19 million cases reported in 1990. Notably, data from the Global Burden of Diseases (GBD) study for the period 1990–2019 indicate that the Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALY) associated with gastritis – reflecting disability and years of life lost due to premature mortality – decreased from 48.1 to 34.8 per 100,000 population. However, despite this reduction, the total number of affected patients has continued to rise [3]. According to the 2021 estimates of the Global Burden of Diseases study, the number of patients with gastritis was higher among women than men, and the incidence rate increased with age. Statistical data indicate that gastritis typically begins to appear in middle age, with the highest prevalence observed in individuals aged 40–59 years [4]. Studies conducted in Uzbekistan indicate that approximately 80% of the population is infected with *Helicobacter pylori* [2]. Among the main treatment approaches for *Helicobacter pylori* infection, regimens containing amoxicillin and furazolidone have demonstrated the highest eradication efficacy in previously untreated patients.

The date of treatment, the patient's age, the selected antibiotic regimen, and the duration of therapy have been identified as risk factors contributing to unsuccessful *H. pylori* eradication. In addition, it has been observed that the results of the post-eradication Urease Breath Test (UBT) tend to cluster around the established cut off value in many cases [5]. The study included medical records of a total of 186 patients. The overall eradication success rate was 77.4%. The results indicated that the reduction in eradication efficacy was significantly associated with the presence of diabetes and smoking status, with statistical significance values of $p < 0.001$ and $p < 0.004$, respectively. These findings suggest that the standard triple therapy for *Helicobacter pylori* eradication demonstrates lower efficacy compared to the optimal standards recommended in the literature and clinical guidelines. Given the declining effectiveness of this treatment worldwide, the use of alternative regimens and protocols as first-line therapy may be necessary. Further studies are required to assess treatment efficacy across different regional settings [1]. In Uzbekistan, 21 medications with internationally recognized non-proprietary names used for the treatment of gastritis have been registered under a total of 200 trade names. Analysis of these drugs by manufacturer country shows that 55% are from foreign countries, 37.5% are produced by local pharmaceutical companies, and 7.5% are registered by countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) [6]. The above-mentioned studies have addressed gastritis, its prevalence, treatment approaches, and included retrospective analyses of the medical records of hospitalized patients, as well as recommendations for the use of specific medications during therapy. These studies underscore the relevance and necessity of conducting similar research in the context of Uzbekistan, both to retrospectively analyze the medications used for gastritis treatment and to perform

pharmacoeconomic frequency-based analyses. The objective of this study was to conduct a retrospective analysis of the medical records of hospitalized patients with gastritis and to perform a pharmacoeconomic frequency-based analysis of the medications used in their treatment.

Methods. In the study were analyzed medical cards of inpatients treated for gastritis in the Gastroenterology Department of the Multidisciplinary Clinic of Tashkent State Medical University from 2018 to May 2025. The research employed methods such as retrospective analysis, comparison, grouping, statistical processing, and pharmacoeconomic frequency-based anal-

ysis. Among the pharmacoeconomic methods, the frequency-based analysis is a type of quantitative assessment that reflects the recommendation or non-recommendation of specific medications solely based on evidence of their actual use in patient treatment.

Results and Discussions. In our study, analyses were conducted on the age, sex, and frequency of medication use among patients with gastritis. In the first stage of the research were analyzed the number of patients treated for gastritis and their sex distribution at the Multidisciplinary Clinic of Tashkent State Medical University. The results of this analysis are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Analysis of inpatients with gastritis by gender

The study analyzed the distribution of patients by gender. It was found that the number of female patients was higher than that of male patients. In 2018, the total number of treated patients was 88, of which 38.64% were men and 61.36% were women.

Analysis of patient data from 2018 to 2025 revealed that the total number of treated patients was highest in 2018, followed by a gradual decrease during 2019–2021. The lowest patient count was observed in 2022. Notably, in 2020, the clinic's gastroenterology department suspended operations due to the COVID-19

pandemic. In the next stage of our research, an analysis of patients by age was conducted (Figure 2). Patients were primarily treated between the ages of 18–90. The highest morbidity was determined to correspond to patients aged 20–29. Among the patients treated at the clinic, those in the 20–39 and 60–69 age ranges particularly predominate. Accordingly, in 2018, patients aged 20–29 were treated in relatively larger numbers; in 2019, those aged 30–39; and in 2023, those aged 60–69.

Figure 2. Age-based analysis of patients with gastritis

The age distribution of patients was analyzed, and the hypothesis test revealed that the mean number of patients differed significantly from zero, $t(7) = 5.49$, $p < 0.05$. These results indicate that in the hospital, a higher number of patients was observed in the older age group, particularly among those aged 60–69 years, and show a positive deviation of the overall mean from zero. This supports the presence of the studied condition within the population.

Analysis of the demographics of patients treated at the clinic revealed that patients residing in rural areas outnumbered those living in urban areas. The results of this analysis are presented in Figure 3. Between 2018 and 2025, a total of 182 patients (64.54%) from rural areas and 100 patients (35.46%) from urban areas were treated at the clinic.

Figure 3. Demographic analysis of patients treated for gastritis.

The subsequent phase of our research involved analyzing the regional distribution of patients who visited the clinic for gastritis treatment (Table 1).

Table 1.

Analysis of patients treated for gastritis by region

№	Administrative regions	Years							Total number
		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2025	
1	Tashkent city	34	6	–	14	–	12	–	66
2	Tashkent region	14	10	–	8	2	4	4	42
3	Fergana region	2	4	–	–	–	–	–	6
4	Andijan region	2	2	2	2	–	4	2	14
5	Kashkadarya region	10	6	–	6	2	12	8	44
6	Surkhandarya region	8	6	2	6	–	2	–	24
7	Namangan region	–	–	–	2	–	–	–	2
8	Khorezm region	–	6	–	4	–	6	–	16
9	Jizzakh region	6	8	–	–	–	10	–	24
10	Navoi region	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
11	Samarkand region	–	–	2	–	–	–	–	2
12	Sirdaryo region	2	6	–	–	–	2	–	10
13	Bukhara region	4	2	–	–	–	4	–	10
14	Republic of Karakalpakstan	4	4	–	2	2	8	–	20
15	across the Republic of Uzbekistan	88	60	6	44	6	64	14	282

At the Tashkent State Medical University Multi-disciplinary Clinic, the majority of patients treated for gastritis were from Tashkent city, Kashkadarya region, and Tashkent region. Over a period of five years, 66 patients from Tashkent city and 216 patients from the regions visited the clinic either by referral or on their own initiative. Additionally, between 2018 and 2025, out of a total of 282 patients, 112 (39.7%) were treated

under the state-funded referral system, while 170 (60.3%) received treatment at their own expense. Notably, in 2018, two patients from Kazakhstan were also treated at the clinic.

In the next stage of our study, patient diagnostic indicators were analyzed according to the different forms of the disease (Table 2).

Table 2

Analysis of patients' diagnoses by disease forms in gastritis

№	Patient diagnosis names	Absolute number	Relative share, %
1	Erosive gastritis	4	1,4
2	Subatrophic gastritis	2	0,7
3	Chronic atrophic gastritis	20	7,1
4	Chronic gastritis	36	12,8
5	Chronic gastritis A	6	2,1
6	Chronic gastritis B	208	73,8
7	Chronic superficial gastritis	4	1,4
8	Chronic unspecified gastritis	2	0,7
	Total number and share	282	100

According to the analysis, between 2018 and 2025, the majority of patients treated at the clinic were diagnosed with chronic gastritis B (73.8%), chronic gastritis (12.8%), and chronic atrophic gastritis (7.1%). The average length of hospital stay for patients with gastritis was 9 days; however, based on the overall condition of the patients, treatment could range from 5 to 7 days.

In the next stage of the study, medical records of 282 hospitalized patients were reviewed to investigate the pharmaco-economic frequency of drug use in the treatment of the disease. The results of the analysis are presented in the following tables.

Table 3

Pharmacoeconomic frequency analysis of the use of medications applied in the treatment of gastritis disease

№	International nonproprietary name	Dosage Form	Dosage of Medications	Usage Frequency (Relative to the Number of Patients)	Total Sum of Usage	Relative share (relative to the number of patients)	Total quantity of medications used (pieces)
1	Omeprazole	Capsules	20 mg	192	194	68.8%	3004
		Lyophilized powder for injection (vial)	40 mg	2			14
2	Rabeprazole	Capsules	20 mg	34	34	12 %	578
3	Pantoprazole	Tablets	40 mg	34	36	12,7 %	334
		Lyophilized powder for injection (vial)	40 mg	2			10
4	Esomeprazole	Tablets	20 mg	4	6	2,1 %	40
			40 mg	2			20
5	Bismuth tripotassium dicitrate	Tablets	120 mg	16	16	5,6 %	392
6	Metoclopramide	Solution for injection	0,5 %, 2 ml	218	220	78 %	1232
		Tablets	10 mg	2			16
7	Drotaverine	Solution for injection(ampoule)	2 %, 2 ml	168	168	59,5%	961
8	Pancreatin	Enteric-coated tablets	25 DU (100 mg)	118	118	41,8%	2802
9	Activated charcoal	Tablets	250 mg	136	136	48,2 %	3382
10	Aluminum and magnesium compounds Aluminum hydroxide, Magnesium hydroxide, Simethicone	Oral suspension		58	58	20,5%	58
11	Aluminum and magnesium compounds Aluminum hydroxide, Magnesium hydroxide	Oral suspension		12	12	4,2 %	12
12	Aluminum and magnesium compounds Aluminum hydroxide, Magnesium hydroxide, Benzocaine	Oral suspension		4	4	1,4 %	4
13	Lactulose	Syrup in a bottle	667 mg/ml	10	10	3,5%	10
14	Mebeverine hydrochloride	Capsules	200 mg	6	6	2,1 %	80
15	Procaine	Solution for injection	0,5%, 10 ml	184	184	65,2 %	1288
16	Amitriptyline	Tablets	25 mg	60	64	22,7 %	382

		Solution for injection	10 mg/2 ml	4			28
17	Clarithromycin	Tablets	500 mg	2	8	2,8 %	40
			625 mg	2			28
			1000 mg	4			80
18	Sodium chloride + sodium acetate	Solution for infusion	200 ml	96	96	34 %	96
19	Metronidazole	Tablets	200 mg	10	88	31,2 %	210
			250 mg	48			934
		Solution for intravenous infusion, vial	500 mg/100 ml 100 ml (vial)	30			264

According to Table 3, among the main drugs used for the treatment of gastritis, proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) were analyzed for pharmacoeconomic frequency based on their international nonproprietary names (INN). Omeprazole capsules accounted for 75% of the total PPI usage, rabeprazole capsules for 14.45%, and pantoprazole tablets for 8.35%. The relatively high use of omeprazole can be explained by its affordability, popularity, and availability in the clinic's medication supply system. Additionally, activated charcoal 250 mg tablets – 3,382 units, and pancreatin 25 dose units (TBU) tablets – 2,802 units were used. The pharmacoeconomic frequency of recommending these medications to patients was observed to be high. Regarding

drug use relative to the number of patients, metoclopramide ranked first, being administered to 220 of 282 patients (78%). Omeprazole was second, used in 194 patients (68.8%), and procaine was third, administered to 184 patients (65.2%). These results reflect the usage of each drug analyzed individually by its INN. As noted above, medications from the PPI pharmacological group are considered the main drugs for gastritis treatment. Analysis of usage frequency relative to the number of patients shows that PPI drugs were used in 270 of 282 patients (95.74%). Furthermore, analysis of the total quantity of drugs used revealed that a total of 4,000 units were administered.

Table 4
Pharmacoeconomic frequency analysis of the recommendation of proton pump inhibitor medications after inpatient treatment

№	International nonproprietary name	Dosage Form	Dosage of Medications	Number of patients prescribed the medication	Relative proportion of patients prescribed the medications, in percentage
1	Omeprazole + domperidone	Capsules	20 mg + 30 mg	18	6,67
2	Rabeprazole	Capsules	20 mg	96	35,55
3	Rabeprazole + domperidone	Capsules	20 mg + 30 mg	2	0,74
4	Pantoprazole	Tablets	20 mg	10	3,7
			40 mg	68	25,18
5	Pantoprazole + domperidone	Capsules	40 mg + 30 mg	24	8,9
6	Esomeprazole	Tablets	20 mg	22	8,15
			40 mg	30	11,12
	Total number			270	100

Analysis of the patient's medical records revealed that proton pump inhibitors medications were recommended to be taken for 20–30 days after inpatient treatment. According to the data presented in Table 4, the highest prescription rates were observed for 'Rabeprazole' 20 mg capsules and 'Pantoprazole' 40 mg tablets

Conclusion

1. The analysis covered the gender, age, demographic characteristics, regional distribution, and pharmacotherapy process of patients treated for gastritis.

2. Based on the medical records of patients treated for gastritis, it was determined that medications with international non-proprietary names—such as omeprazole, activated charcoal, and pancreatin—were used most frequently, indicating higher pharmacoeconomic frequency and associated costs.

3. The various forms of gastritis, their treatment characteristics, the recommended medications, their pharmaco-economic usage frequency, and the proportion relative to the total number of patients were identified.

4. The retrospective analysis of the medical records of hospitalized patients with gastritis serves as a basis for future pharmaco-economic evaluations of medication provision, improving treatment effectiveness, and minimizing healthcare expenditures.

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